

Synthesis and Physiological Activity of Hydroxyaryl Isoxazoles

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The synthesis of a few 3- α -hydroxy- β -naphthyl and 3-(4-hydroxy-3-biphenyl)-5-aryl isoxazoles has been carried out for elucidating the antibacterial and antifungal properties. The chalcone dibromide method has been utilised for making these compounds. Among the compounds tested, 3- α -hydroxy- β -naphthyl-5-0-methoxyphenyl isoxazole exhibited the maximum activity to both bacteria and fungii.

In an earlier communication¹ the synthesis and physiological activity of 3-hydroxyphenyl-5-aryl isoxazoles have been described. In continuation, a few 3- α -hydroxy- β -naphthyl and 3-(4-hydroxy-3-biphenyl)-5-aryl isoxazoles have been prepared with a view to ascertaining their antibacterial and antifungal properties. The choice of the naphthyl and hydroxybiphenyl moieties in these isoxazoles is based on the significant physiological activities that have earlier been reported for these compounds^{2,3,4}.

Of the various available routes to prepare the isoxazoles, the chalcone dibromide method⁵ has been utilised in the present investigation, not only due to the unambiguous course of the reaction but also due to the easy accessibility of the starting materials needed, viz., substituted benzaldehydes and aryl methyl ketones.

The hydroxychalcones (I) were prepared by the condensation of substituted benzaldehydes with 2-acetyl-1-naphthol and 3-acetyl-4-hydroxy biphenyl in alcohol in the presence of 30% sodium hydroxide at 60° for 3 hr. in 50-60% yields. The two ketones required

SCHEME-I

for this reaction were obtained by the Fries rearrangement of α -naphthylacetate⁶ and 4-acetoxybiphenyl⁷ respectively. The chalcones(I) were then converted to the corresponding dibromides (II) with bromine in ether or chloroform or carbon disulphide in almost quantitative yields. Finally, the chalcone dibromides were cyclised to the 3 : 5-disubstituted isoxazoles (III) using hydroxylamine hydrochloride and potassium hydroxide in 50-60% yields. The isoxazoles and their analytical data are given in the Table.

Bacteriostatic activity : Of the eleven compounds tested for the bacteriostatic activity, 3- α -hydroxy- β -naphthyl-5-*o*-methoxyphenyl isoxazole has been found to be the most active and inhibited the growth of the three bacteria used, namely, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus subtilis*. 5-*p*-Chlorophenyl derivative, which has been found to be inactive to E.C. and B.S. at 100 p.p.m., is however active against S.A. even at 2 p.p.m. The 5-(3 : 4-methylenedioxyphenyl) analogue has been found to be active at 5 p.p.m. to S.A. and at 100 p.p.m. to E.C. and B.S. The parent, i.e., 3- α -hydroxy- β -naphthyl-5-phenyl isoxazole, has not shown any significant activity. The biphenyl isoxazoles have been found to be inactive.

Fungistatic activity : In the case of fungistatic testing also, the maximum activity against the fungi used, *Aspergillus niger*, was shown by the 5-*o*-methoxyphenyl derivative. Its percentage inhibition has been found to be 90, 75 and 45 at 100, 10, and 5 p.p.m. respectively. This was followed in order by 5-(3 : 4-methylenedioxyphenyl) and 5-*p*-chlorophenyl derivatives whose percentage inhibitions have been found to be 80 and 60 respectively at 100 p.p.m. In these tests also the biphenyl isoxazoles did not show activity.

EXPERIMENTAL

General procedures :

1) **Chalcones :** The appropriate aldehyde and ketone were mixed in equimolar quantities in alcohol solution and treated with sodium hydroxide (30% aq.). The reaction mixture was kept at 60° on a water bath for about 3 hr. and the chalcone isolated by acidification. The chalcone was recrystallised from alcohol. The following chalcones are reported for the first time :

- (1) 1'-Hydroxy-3-(*p*-dimethylaminophenyl)-2'-acrylonaphthone, m.p. 90°, (Found : N, 4.4; Calcd. N, 4.4%).
- (2) 1'-Hydroxy-3-(*p*-chlorophenyl)2'-acrylonaphthone, m.p. 95°, (Found : C, 73.6; H, 4.1; Calcd : C, 73.8; H, 4.2%).
- (3) 1'-Hydroxy-3-*o*-chlorophenyl-2'-acrylonaphthone, m.p. 156°, (Found : C, 73.7; H, 4.3; Calcd : C, 73.8; H, 4.2%).
- (4) 2'-Hydroxy-5'-phenyl chalcone, m.p. 112°, (Found : C, 84.1; H, 5.2; Calcd : C, 84.0; H, 5.3%).
- (5) 2'-Hydroxy-5'-phenyl-4-methoxy chalcone, m.p. 140°, (Found : C, 80.1; H, 5.4; Calcd : C, 80.0; H, 5.5%).

TABLE
Hydroxyaryl isoxazoles

Isoxazole		m.p. (°C)	Mol. formula	%Nitrogen	
3-Substituent	5-Substituent			Calcd.	Found
α -Hydroxy- β -naphthyl	Phenyl	170	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ O ₂ N	4.9	5.0
α -Hydroxy- β -naphthyl	3 : 4-Methylenedioxyphenyl	156	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ O ₄ N	4.2	4.1
α -Hydroxy- β -naphthyl	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	193	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ O ₃ N	4.4	4.3
α -Hydroxy- β -naphthyl	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	146	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ O ₃ N	4.4	4.3
α -Hydroxy- β -naphthyl	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	195	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂	8.4	8.5
α -Hydroxy- β -naphthyl	<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminophenyl	205	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂	8.5	8.4
α -Hydroxy- β -naphthyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	162	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ O ₂ NCl	4.3	4.3
α -Hydroxy- β -naphthyl	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	160	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ O ₂ NCl	4.3	4.4
α -Hydroxy- β -naphthyl	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	175	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ O ₂ NCl ₂	3.9	3.8
4-Hydroxy-3-biphenyl	Phenyl	265	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₂ N	4.5	4.5
4-Hydroxy-3-biphenyl	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	270	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₃ N	3.2	3.4

Note : All the melting points are uncorrected. Satisfactory analyses are obtained for carbon and hydrogen also in the case of all the isoxazoles.

2) *Chalcone dibromides* : The chalcone (0.01 mole) in ether or chloroform or carbon-disulphide was treated with bromine solution (0.01 mole) in the same solvent with cooling and stirring. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with little cold ether and recrystallised from alcohol. The following dibromides are reported for the first time :

- (1) 1'-Hydroxy-3-phenyl-2'-acrylonaphthone dibromide, m.p. 185°, (Found : C, 52.4; H, 3.4; Calcd : C, 52.5; H, 3.2%).
- (2) 1'-Hydroxy-3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-2'-acrylonaphthone dibromide, m.p. 130°, (Found : C, 51.5; H, 3.3; Calcd : C, 51.7; H, 3.4%).
- (3) 1'-Hydroxy-3(*o*-nitrophenyl)-2'-acrylonaphthone dibromide, m.p. 235°, (Found : N, 2.9; Calcd : N, 2.9%).
- (4) 1'-Hydroxy-3(*p*-dimethylaminophenyl)-2'-acrylonaphthone dibromide, m.p. 122°, (Found : N, 2.8; Calcd : N, 2.9%).
- (5) 1'-Hydroxy-3(*p*-chlorophenyl)-2'-acrylonaphthone dibromide, m.p. 135°, (Found : C, 48.7; H, 2.7; Calcd : C, 48.6; H, 2.8%).
- (6) 1'-Hydroxy-3(*o*-chlorophenyl)-2'-acrylonaphthone dibromide, m.p. 156°, (Found : C, 48.5; H, 2.6; Calcd : C, 48.6; H, 2.8%).
- (7) 1'-Hydroxy-3-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-2'-acrylonaphthone dibromide, m.p. 225°, (Found : C, 45.3; H, 2.5; Calcd : C, 45.3; H, 2.4%).

- (8) 2'-Hydroxy-5'-phenyl chalcone dibromide, m.p. 177°, (Found : C, 54.8; H, 3.4; Calcd : C, 54.8; H, 3.5%).
- (9) 2'-Hydroxy-5'-phenyl-4-methoxy chalcone dibromide, m.p. 180°, (Found : C, 52.8; H, 3.6; Calcd : C, 52.9; H, 3.7%).

3) *Isoxazoles* : The dibromide (0.01 mole) was dissolved by boiling in alcohol and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.01 mole aq., saturated solution) was added followed by potassium hydroxide (30% aq.). The mixture was allowed to stand for about 10 min. and the isoxazole was isolated by acidification. Recrystallization was effected from alcohol or benzene.

Physiological testing : Tube dilution method⁸ was adopted to evaluate the bacteriostatic activity and three representative bacteria, viz., *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus subtilis* were employed as test organisms. The fungistatic activity was assessed by the radial growth measurement technique⁹ and *Aspergillus niger* was the test organism.

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